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The Mediatiation of Values and Norms
in Religious and Secular Wedding Narratives

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Ten Best Practices for Wedding Photographers and Videographers

1. **Diverse Photos:** In addition to romantic idealized shots, include humorous photos. Couples cherish these images, finding their weddings often livelier than depicted.
2. **Individuality of the Couple:** Capture the groom and bride separately or with their friends, showcasing their distinct personalities even within marriage.
3. **Gender Representation:** Challenge stereotypical portrayals of the vulnerable bride and protective groom. Play with gender roles, injecting humor or reversing stereotypes to broaden the spectrum of wedding photo motifs.
4. **Fresh Motifs:** Consult the couple's preferences and avoid clichéd motifs like the traditional romantic couple photo.
5. **Significance of Guests in a Multifaceted Atmosphere:** Group photos play a crucial role in commemorating the wedding attendees and capturing a range of emotions, from joyous and playful to serious and weary. These images encapsulate the diverse array of feelings experienced by both the wedding guests and the couple, immortalizing a day filled with varied emotions.
6. **Ceremony Venue:** While the ceremony location holds significance as the site of the ritual, it's essential not to overemphasize it in photos, acknowledging that the wedding unfolds beyond this single space.
7. **Wedding Reception:** Due to the less structured nature of receptions, photos may lack focus and meaning. Consider utilizing short videos to better capture the atmosphere, which can be compiled into a cohesive wedding reception montage or reportage.
8. **Digital Preservation:** Encourage couples to safeguard their digital copies, as digitally stored photos often become lost, particularly when stored solely on smartphones.
9. **Smartphone Contributions:** Invite guests to share photos captured on their smartphones, as these snapshots often offer surprising and unique perspectives of the wedding.
10. **Memory Creation through Photos:** Be aware that your photos and videos create memories. Capture moments from the ceremony and reception that the couple may have missed due to nerves or distractions, creating lasting memories of their special day.

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